

A Study of Job Stress Level and Performance of Female Teachers at Higher Educational Institutions

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: January 16, 2023</p> <p>Accepted: April 17, 2023</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Job Stress, Depression, Academic Problems, Marital Status, Questionnaire.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7834322</p>	<p><i>The study was aimed at discovering the levels of job stress among female university teachers of Karachi in private sector. The research was based on quantitative in nature for which some research questions were developed to collect the data from one hundred teachers randomly through questionnaire. The research questions were based on marital status, financial problems, Academic problems, Administrative involvement, and environmental aspect as well. The sample was taken from Jinnah University for Women Karachi. The result revealed that besides all these factors and problems they are working successfully and devotedly. It was concluded that there is direct relationship between job stress and teachers performance. The study recommended that female university teachers should be encouraged to have a positive attitude towards their further grooming, supporting attitude of administration in resolving the academic affairs through higher studies as well as they should be encouraged for their further higher studies and professional improvement.</i></p>

Introduction

Education defines the direction of the career. Perhaps, throughout the world and particularly in Asiatic society, major investigation is, "what do you want to do" to the students from kindergarten to universities. Interestingly, most respondents include their answer on the biases of social, environmental and cultural and their parents' background. This means that factors affecting career choice will be culturally different from culture and community in society. Usually, students must pursue higher education in wishes with higher employment opportunities. Ethical and basic reasons consider education as socially valuable and important work. It consists of some aspects of professional activities such as youth's education and education in universities subjects. It concludes in a lot of studies that many reasons based on basic conceptions. . In this regard, "the basic value of a career" shows that this person is a passionate, and enjoys passion of teaching. Similarly, teaching is capable of discovering the characteristics of those who have a well interested, if we want to encourage people to teach (Kuala Lumpur and Kiquou, 2002). Uzbek (2007), explain that lecturer doesn't chose their profession on social and economic reasons but the factors relate to their personal motives. In addition, in a few other researches acknowledged that people prefer education as their status because of an independent line of work, at the same time others consider that it is the profession to deal with youth and in this environment they feel him a young person.

Interested persons for teaching considered it is a contribution for humanity, healthy salary, attractive work schedule and job protection with long leaves (Kawai and Lewis, 2002, Noblech, 2005; Stiegelbauer, 1992; Heis, 2000).

To consider everything, it is clear that the teacher chooses his career for a variety of reasons. Therefore, the purpose of this study is that the future teachers should be the best teaching professionals. It also checks that variables such as area, gender, family background, grade and age create a major distinction where they live and serve.

Women are considered as the integral parts of any society and are meant as one of the strong pillar in accomplishing a nation, society or a community. Their role has always been recognized as important as men do. When it comes in the field of education and educational institutes, women too have played a major role and they have contributed in the field of education. Their contribution towards education has always impacted the society and influenced the generations across. Woman plays tremendous role as being leaders since they already have the capacity to perform or control several of task at the same time. Thus if we watch out any educational institution we can see that there are few female leaders.

According to an economist (2015), Woman is able to handle any situation there is possibilities that woman to be a leader in various sector, such as government sector, corporate region, and in academy. But still woman are considered less than man due to gender inequality. The leadership of woman is less found in various institutions. Bono et al (2017); Eagly, ET all (2003) state that women have competencies that are compare to men. In the

world for a smooth efficient and productive work of an organization an effective leadership is one of the greatest way of leading an institution.

According to Atkinson 1981; Moran, 1992; and Oplatke, 2006 and many other research studies are found under representative of acceptable woman in guidance. In India higher education and administration the scene is similar to the women's most education and profession (Ramachandran, 2003). The field of relationship has historically been dominated by men but it being challenged by the increasing number of women leader in the workplace. furthermore, evidence suggest that women's leadership style is also an obstacle for women .first because of this differences in the style of women leadership and the use of force between women current power culture at the top of the organizations .

Second because women experience double binding behavior, which mean's when emphasizing them the style of feminine leadership, they are considered less authorized leaders. When using masculine leadership style, they are negatively approved breaking their gender role (Eagly and Karav 2002).

The history of women in work, social context of women lives describes in education that how much women able to control and manage the situation. Mostly when women join the education sector the aim is to bring "change" the status. Women more identify the educational career due to their social justice experiences than men. Commitment to social justice is documented in a number of studies that isolate social justice as an initial motivator as well as a continuing mission, (Sanders, Lawson, 2001; Shapiro, 2004; Smith Campbell, 2002; Strachan, 1999-2002). The women have efforts to know the importance of instructional program and try to complicate the task.

Mayor and L. (1993) separate three factors of professional commitment: affective commitment' (profession's progress determines the strongest desire to live in positive emotions and occupation), 'normative commitment' (determination in the meaning of responsibility and stay in this profession) and "commitment to continuity" (commitment to awareness about the costs of leaving the profession.

Stress is a dynamic condition in which an individual faces so many issues in the society. Anyone in job can have the worst condition specially in the developing countries where mostly in the family both male and female do the job to maintain and secure the family but having different types of stresses they have adverse effects on physical and mental ability.

The concept of stress was first introduced in the life sciences by Hans Selye in the year 1936, so many researches proved that excessive job stress can lead the long term health issues like cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, blood pressure, muscular pain, depression and anxiety.

Following stresses have adverse effects on Physical health & mental ability

a. Physical Health

- (i) Sleeplessness (ii) Social withdrawal (iii) Tension (iv) muscle pain
- (v) Stomach problem

b. Mental Health

- (i) Anxiety & ill-tempered (ii) Lack of interest (iii) less attention towards work (iv) Lack of concentration (v) Slow speed of thinking.

Bennet (1994) quoted stress as a wide gathering of physical and mental manifestations that out comes from challenges experienced by an individual while endeavoring to adjust a domain. As far as the teachers stress are concerned, they are faced many problems such as frustration , lack of attention towards performance, distraction by other colleagues, weak bonding with student teachers relationship and rowdy which directly affects not only academically but domestically as well.

Objectives of Study

- To identify the main causes of stress at work.
- To assess effects of job related stress on teacher's performance.
- To observe the effects of organizational stress on teacher's performance.
- To find out the effects of marital status on teacher's performance.
- To examine the effects of financial stress on teacher's performance.

Hypotheses of the Study

Three Hypotheses were developed which are:

H₁: There is relation between the job stress and the teachers' performance.

H₂: There is relation between teachers' performance and institutional stress.

H₃: There is relation between the job stress and effect of marital status.

Justification of Study

This study was completed on the basis of present advancement of technology in the teaching learning process as teacher acted always as a guide or facilitator to reduce the stress of student. According to Payne & Donaghy 2010 every living being is always under stress but realizes it only when it is unable to handle it. Lupier McEwen , Gunnar & Heim quoted in 2009. "Stress affects the mind body, behavior and daily functioning as well as relationship"

It is a fact that stress comes not only in job but in the environment, and colleagues' relationships too while sometimes it may be caused by their personal or domestic problems which affects on their performance. Teachers' stresses are followed by the factors below as well.

- A. Intensity of work . (Overloaded work , quick changes)
- B. Students Behavior .(Less respect , students behavior and attitude)
- C. Professional Growth . (In sufficient time, no up to date knowledge)
- D. Extrinsic Annoyer (Non cooperation of administration , problems with colleagues)

No doubt teacher job satisfaction plays a pivotal role in the teaching learning process which affects throughout her performance.

Significance of the Study

The study provides guidelines and confidence to policy makers of education administrators as well as other public sector and private sector organizations. It helps the all stack-holders of organization to cope their deficiencies in recruitment process and job description. Job designs are the basics components for any profession where job stress very easily affects employee especially female faculty. This study discovers the job design and employee satisfaction at university level in Pakistan. By the findings of the study Ministry of Education, HEC, and administration can assess their teacher perfection and quality of teacher recruitment process ensure quality assurance in the university education. All flaws and deficiencies also highlighted which should be solved and to fulfill the training process by teacher training institutions.

The study provides guide lines for policy makers and think tanks for education to improve policies of education for international competition. Satisfaction level after adopting teaching profession especially females will highlight teacher's inner feeling about profession and government of Pakistan can suggest materialistic difference between other jobs in the country to improve this profession.

Review of the Related Literature

As far as the stress is concerned the teachers are more prone to stress because dealing with students all day is itself a stressful occupation. Actually education is a continuous process which develops the required ability, attitude, discipline and behavior for life while many scholars accepted the teachers' importance and quoted many times about teachers as maker of a man and architect of future. But a disorganized classroom without routines and expectations make it difficult for the teacher to do her job properly and the teacher loses the crucial teaching time. Classroom management creates a set of expectations used in an organized classroom environment. A teacher with classroom management skills creates consistency for her students. This research was conducted in the present situations and the advancement of technologies and strategies. The teachers act as guide and facilitators to reduce the psychological stress among students at university level.

Stress is the factor that affects the activities of teachers as well. It has been observed that stress is an important concern in every institution and over burden them which affects their services they are providing. No doubt the term stress can either entuse pressure or may create strain which in turn might be negative and if this condition is totally hostile, it may turn into distressful situation.

According to a survey made by smith, Segal and Jaffe (2007), if depression or anxiety is associated with work then there will be 13.5 million losses of working days. It means that it is necessary for the administration to manage the welfare of teachers directly and ensure a nonstop work without any kind of sick leaves and absenteeism levels. Better availability of the resources may satisfy the teachers and force them to do the work efficiently and effectively. In modern time work life balance is very necessary due to the availability of new technology and trends so stress of the teachers are decreasing day by day and working through these technologies makes a work easier. Work becomes more interesting when your colleagues are supportive and helpful (Shukla, 2014).

Conceptual Framework

Research Methodology

- This Study was designed on quantitative based approach.
- Population was all 350 teachers of Jinnah University for Women Nazimabad Karachi Pakistan (Gay, Mills & Airasian, 2009).
- Out of 350 Faculty members, only 100 teachers were randomly selected from four Faculties (Social Sciences, Sciences, Pharmacy and Business Administration) as sample.
- A close – ended questionnaire, consisting 20 items was administered to all 100 faculty members.
- The questionnaire was prepared, on Likert Scale.
- Reliability and validity was checked through Pilot testing. The reliability was found to be 0.83.
- The questionnaires was distributed and collected personally from the teacher's of the university.

Data Analysis

Data was collected through questionnaire. Actually questionnaire was the best tool to collect the information, so it was distributed to the respondents throughout the university randomly. The collected data of 100 respondents was analyzed statistically. Hypotheses were tested with the help of Correlation coefficient (r) and obtained the findings accurately.

Table 1 Correlation coefficient between job stress and Teachers Performance

Variables	N	r	P
Overall job stress and the teachers' performance	100	-0.40	0.001

Table 1 showed that correlation coefficient between job stress and Teachers Performance ($P=0.001$) and it has been negative, so there is direct relationship between job stress and Teachers Performance.

Table 2 Correlation coefficient between Institutional stress and Teachers Performance

Variables	N	r	P
Institutional stress and the teachers' performance	100	-0.20	0.001

Table 2 indicated that correlation coefficient between institutional stress and the teachers' performance ($P=0.001$) and it has been negative, so there is direct relationship between institutional stress and teachers performance.

Table 3 Correlation coefficient between marital stress and teachers' performance

Variables	N	r	P
Marital stress and the teachers' performance	100	0.26	0.001

Table 3 indicated that correlation coefficient between marital stress and the teachers' performance ($P=0.001$) and it has been positive, so there is direct relationship between institutional stress and teachers performance.

Discussion and Conclusion

Stress is due to mental computer work and emotional pressure which is due to feelings and behaviour of others members working in the institution. They might be an intensity of work, students behavior some times and professional growth as well. Furthermore this study revealed that the teachers are affected for their hesitating nature or lack of interest towards subjects becomes the cause of stress. On the other side lack of command on knowledge and skills or curriculum aspects in teaching learning process is also the matter of stress and depression. Hanif, Tarir and Nadeem (2011) revealed that negative significant relationship exists between teachers stress and job performance. Azizollah, Zaman, khaled & Razieh (2013) showed that there is negative correlation between job stress and performance. Daniel (2019) proved that stress had a negative effect on performance of employees.

It was concluded that there is direct relationship between job stress and teachers performance. On the whole this study revealed the positive and significant results regarding teachers job satisfaction, stress and depression. Joy and Kumar (2018) found that sources of job stress are inversely related to job performance and role ambiguity exerts great impact on job performance along with fear of obsolescence and workload. Nawaz and Ansari (2017) supported the association between job stress and job performance. It might be overcome through effective environment, motivation, encouragement and self-respect as well. Which has been observed and analyzed that. The above mentioned factors would be used by institution, colleagues and home; it would be for the betterment of the university/ institutions and teachers themselves too.

Recommendations

- Job performance may be improved if relationship with senior colleagues is pleasant.
- Motivation or any other incentive in job may improve the performance of teachers.
- Responsibilities are clearly defined at the time of appointment.
- There must be a friendly relationship with management.
- Well defined organizational structure is in existence to ensure smooth flow of information to teachers.
- Organizational climate and working conditions must be favorable.
- Monthly salary should be well enough for their family financial strength.
- Proper policies and procedures should be communicated to decrease the job stress
- Laugh can decrease the stress so teachers are suggested to laugh which will activate their body relaxation.
- A balanced life should be kept between job and home environment to maintain the mental relaxation.
- The study may be extended at the secondary school level, which will explore more factors.
- A comparative study may be attempted between teacher job satisfaction in the public sector and private sector to bring out the proper results.

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